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2. MEĐUNARODNI KONGRES TRAUMATOLOŠKE ASOCIJACIJE JUGOISTOČNE SRBIJE

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2. MEĐUNARODNI KONGRES TRAUMATOLOŠKE ASOCIJACIJE JUGOISTOČNE SRBIJE

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**PRELOMI POTKOLENICE LEČENI SPOLJNIM FIKSATOROM
NA ODELJENJU ZA ORTOPEDIJU I TRAUMATOLOGIJU
KLINIČKO-BOLNIČKOG CENTRA KOSOVSKA MITROVICA**

**TIBIAL SHAFT FRACTURES TREATED WITH AN
EXTERNAL FIXATOR AT THE DEPARTMENT OF
ORTHOPEDICS AND TRAUMATOLOGY OF THE CLINICAL
HOSPITAL CENTER OF KOSOVSKA MITROVICA**

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Uvod: Prelomi potkolenice su česti prelomi dugih kostiju koji su od velikog značaja u traumatologiji. Uloga spoljne fiksacije kao vida hirurškog lečenja je značajna i široko primenjena. Postoje 3 metode korišćenja spoljašnje fiksacije za lečenje preloma tibije: spoljašnja fiksacija kao primarni i definitivni tretman, spoljašnja fiksacija u kombinaciji sa unutrašnjom fiksacijom i konverzija spoljašnje fiksacije u unutrašnju fiksaciju.

Cilj: Prikazati mogućnosti spoljašnje fiksacije kao definitivnog načina lečenja preloma potkolenice.

Metode: U našem radu smo analizirali 254 preloma potkolenice lečenih spoljnom fiksatorima M20 Mitković, koji su lečeni na Odeljenju ortopedije i traumatologije KBC Kosovska Mitrovica. Ovom serijom obuhvaćeno je 172 muškarca ili 68% od ukupnog broja obolelih i 83 ili 32% žena.

Rezultati: Prosečna starost pacijenata lečenih ovom metodom je između treće i četvrte decenije života. Pad na nogu uz uvrtnje stola ili celog donjeg dela noge je najčešći vid i uzrok povreda u 69%. Zatvoreni prelom potkolenice dijagnostifikovan je kod 220 pacijenata (A AO 59%, B AO 26% i C AO 15%). Adekvatan položaj koštanih fragmenata postignut je metodom zatvorene repozicije kod 90 %, prosečno vreme zarastanja je 18,4 nedelje. Kod 93% pacijenata postigli smo zarastanje kosti.

Zaključak: Jednostavna tehnika postavljanja, jednostavnost instrumentacije i dobri rezultati lečenja proširili su spektar indikacija gde se spoljna fiksacija može koristiti za lečenje preloma potkolenice kao primarni i definitivni način lečenja.

Ključne reči: prelom, potkolenica, spoljašnja, fiksacija.

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Introduction: Tibial shaft fractures are frequent fractures of long bones that are of great importance in traumatology. The role of external fixation as a type of surgical treatment is significant and widely applied. There are 3 methods of using external fixation to treat tibial fractures: external fixation as primary and definitive treatment, external fixation combined with internal fixation, and conversion of external fixation to internal fixation.

Objective: To show the possibilities of external fixation as a definitive way of treating lower leg fractures.

Methods: In our work, we analyzed 254 lower leg fractures treated with SF according to Mitković M20, which were treated at the Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology of CHC Kosovska Mitrovica. This series included 172 men or 68% of the total number of patients, and 83 or 32% women.

Results: The average age of patients treated with this method is between the third and fourth decades of life. Falling on the leg with twisting of the table or the entire lower part of the leg is the most common type and cause of injuries in 69%. A closed lower leg fracture was diagnosed in 220 patients (A AO 59%, B AO 26% and C AO 15%). Adequate position of the bone fragments was achieved by the closed reposition method in 190 (%), the average healing time was 18.4 weeks. In 93% of patients, we achieved bone union.

Conclusion: Simple placement technique, simplicity of instrumentation, and good treatment results have broadened the spectrum of indications where external fixation can be used for the treatment of tibial fractures as a primary and definitive treatment modality.

Key words: fracture, tibia, shaft, external, fixation.